

Q-Fever (Coxiellosis)

Q fever is a disease caused by the **bacterium *Coxiella burnetii***, which can spread from animals to humans. It is typically found in livestock such as cattle, sheep, and goats (when it is known as **Coxiellosis**) but has also been found in various domestic and wild animals.

C. burnetii is shed mainly in **birth products** (birth fluids, placenta), but may also be shed in vaginal mucus, milk, and faeces.

Humans can become infected with the bacteria via inhalation or ingestion.

C. burnetii is **highly resilient**, surviving for months in harsh conditions, making prevention in animals challenging.

A commercial vaccine for coxiellosis is available for livestock in the UK and Europe. The vaccine can **reduce shedding** of the bacteria (**reducing transmission**) and protect against reproductive losses. Injection site reactions are common, and vaccination can cause a drop in milk production particularly after booster vaccination.

Human vaccination is performed for high-risk occupational groups in Australia only. However, the vaccine carries some risks; administering it to individuals previously exposed to *C. burnetii* can lead to abscesses or widespread inflammatory reactions.

Both commercial human and veterinary vaccines are based on whole killed *C. burnetii* bacteria.

Picture of *C. burnetii* bacteria within an infected cell (Photo: ©E. Liebler-Tenorio, FLI)

REPRODIVAC solutions:

We aim to develop **recombinant protein subunit vaccines for coxiellosis** which will be **safer to use and easier to manufacture**. In addition, **complementary diagnostic tests** will be developed with the ability to **discriminate** between **vaccinated and infected animals** which will help with identifying infected animals in a population of vaccinated animals.